

Unveiling the Unspeakable in Ben Jelloun's Translated Novel *Laylet el Qadr*

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Abstract

Maghrebian Francophone Literature has taken the limelight in investigating sexual themes, although it raises many controversies and criticism. Ben Jelloun is among the authors who tackle the different tabooed subjects existing in their societies including female sexuality, rape, adultery, and homosexuality. To this vein, the rationale of the current research paper is to provide an in-depth look on the use of sexual discourse in Arabic literature in general and Maghrebian Francophone Literature in particular. Ultimately, another concern of this research paper is to uncover the main reasons that lead Ben Jelloun to target female sexuality in his novel *Laylet el Qadr (The Sacred Night)*. To fulfill this claim, the present research paper provides an in-depth look at the major tabooed topics, language, and its lexis found in the novel under investigation. To this end, the findings proved that *Laylet el Qadr* tackled the subject of gendered identity and sexuality through addressing the topic of female sexuality. The results also demonstrated that the novel is rich in topics that examine androgyny, rape, adultery, and female sexuality. The analysis confirmed that the tabooed vocabulary employed in the novel describes mainly female body parts and sexual intercourse.

Keywords: Ben Jelloun's *Laylet el Qadr*, female sexuality, taboos, Maghrebian Francophone Literature

Introduction

Violating taboos has become an important character of Moroccan literature in particular, and Maghrebian Francophone libertine fiction. According to Orlando (2009), this type of literature "interrogates the conscience of Moroccan society" (p. 107). The desire of its authors is "to break away from the burden of family and tradition" (p. 107). Consequently, violating taboos in Maghreb's fiction goes beyond what Middle Eastern writers are trying to explore. In effect, investigating gender issues, love, women's dress, and work become old-fashioned in Maghrebian literature. Novelists have turned their attention towards sexuality, and its major topics as marital sex, homosexuality, and lesbianism as will be discussed throughout the present research work.

At first blush, one should inform that Rachid O is the first Francophone Maghrebian author who paves the way for other Moroccan novelists to talk about homosexuality in the Arab world in general, and Moroccan society in particular. For this reason, his works are banned in most Islamic countries, and even in France, but

nowadays they can be found in all French libraries. Indeed, they represent a real image about the status of sexuality, and gender in Morocco such as in “*L’Enfant ébloui*”, through which he indirectly declares his state as a homosexual writer. According to Orlando (2009), the major topics which are presented in his novels “explore the many stratifications that exist in contemporary Moroccan society caused by patriarchy and tradition, family and clan” (p. 113).

From this perspective, one should also add that most Arab writers in general and Moroccan authors, in particular, are interested in distinguishing “literary production and non-normative sexualities in the Maghreb (and indeed other Arab-Muslim regions)” (Ncube, 2014, p. 477). Tied to this idea, one should also assert that this distinction springs from their desires to talk about their own life experiences. For this reason, the works of Rachid O, Taia, and Ben Jelloun can be considered as a part of what is called *auto-fiction*.

Although Moroccan writers treat the subject of homosexuality openly, they are cautious towards female sexuality or they deal with it explicitly as in the case of Nedjma’s *The Almond* in which the novelist shows the sexual relationship between the protagonist Badra, her cousin Noura, and her schoolmate Hazima. In light of this idea, Détrez (2010) avered the following statement:

In the novels of Arab women, sexual relationships among women are depicted with varying degrees of explicitness. In Djébar’s *femme d’Alger dans leur appartement*, same-sex desire is only suggested, but it is explicit in *L’amande* in which Badra and her cousin Noura, Badra and her schoolmate Hazima, Driss’ grandmother and Mabrouka, Najat and Saloua all display same-sex desire. (p. 219)

To this end, the choice of embarking upon this current research sprang from the fact that Arabic literature in general and Meghrebian Francophone novels, in particular, have been characterized by the use of linguistic taboos in relation to the socio-cultural background of the authors’ societies. Thereby, this research aims at identifying taboo lexis found in Ben Jelloun’s translated novel into Arabic *Laylet el Qadr* (*The Sacred Night*). It also implies taking into account the major tabooed subjects that transgress religious and social boundaries, mainly female sexuality, rape, and prostitution, which are regarded as the most tabooed themes. From the foregoing discussion, our research inquiries fall on the ensuing research questions which are presented as follows:

1. What are the main tabooed topics introduced in Ben Jelloun’s translated novel *Laylet el Qadr*?
2. How does Ben Jelloun represent these themes?
3. What are the different types of tabooed lexis found in the novel?

Taking into consideration the above research questions, the following hypotheses can be put forward:

1. Ben Jelloun introduces the subject of female sexuality through which he transgresses the social traditions of the Moroccan society, while the central

theme is female identity. Hence, female sexuality is a motive to regain the lost identity of the protagonist Zahra.

2. Ben Jelloun gives a vivid description of the most tabooed subject starting with female sexuality, then rape, and adultery.
3. Ben Jelloun employs a rich vocabulary to describe body parts especially the female body, genitals, and lexis linked to sexual intercourse.

Literature Review

It is important to affirm that Zahra's efforts, to reach freedom can be regarded as a type of emancipation for her identity, and root. Thereupon, her fight is against the standards of the society through violating its taboos, or the societal barriers because as a female "she is a victim of a paternal decision beyond her control" (Hamil, 2001, p. 65). Uniformly, Gikandi (2003) seemed to share the same view arguing that Ben Jelloun's major fictional works address the unbreakable, and are "concerned with giving voice to Moroccan taboos and exploring the margins of the country's culture" (p. 79).

It seems accepted that *Laylet el Qadr* touches the thinnest line between the sacred, the profane, and the taboo through, firstly, introducing the most tabooed topics in Islam as rape, androgyny, or bisexuality, heterosexuality, and female sexuality. In effect, the addressed novel has also tackled other tabooed subjects rather than sexuality. It reveals some facts concerning the worship of God by some people. A good example is when the Consul is astonished by one of his students' questions when he wonders about the fact that all Christians go to hell, Islam is the best religion and why God waited so long to make it as a first religion (Gikandi, 2003).

At first blush, taboos constitute a large part of Islam in comparison with the sacred thing. Actually, without respecting what is sacred, people can violate the taboos of their society. Up till this point, the female body is sacred, and for this reason, it should be covered. A good example is the use of the word 'hijab' (to cover the body), which is used to cover the hair. On the other hand, the female body has become a symbol of honor for all Muslim societies. El- haik¹ has been mentioned in the novel in purpose because all Maghreb females are obliged to use it (Gikandi, 2003).

Thus far, the bulk behind this title is to review some previous works that analyze the use of taboos in *Laylet el Qadr*. In this context, they can be divided into three main subjects; bisexuality, heterosexuality, and female sexuality.

Bisexuality

Laylet el Qadr (The Sacred Night) is a sequel of *The Sand Child*, through which the protagonist is obliged by her father to live as a man. Zahra has been upbrought as a boy and has no choice to behave as an androgynous or bisexual person. Therefore, she loses her real identity as a female. According to Schellinger (1998), *The Sacred Night* is not a tale, but a revelation of some facts that can be found in most Arab societies, where females have to follow the restrictions put by the family and society. He added that Ben Jelloun shows Zahra as a victim of rape when she wants to free herself from androgyny. Through this rape, she explores the feeling to be a woman, and then she "embarks on a journey of redemption, rediscovery and ultimate deliverance" with the Consul

(Schellinger, 1998, p. 1159). In the same wave of thought, Taylor (2007) asserted that *The Sacred Night* completes the story of *The Sand Child*, which revolves around Ahmed/Zahra as “an androgynous character”, who is “forced to live the first 20 years of his/her life as a male because of Hadj’s desperate desire of a son” (p. 386). He confirmed that Zahra’s father decides to give an exclusive education and upbringing to his daughter so that she will be able to behave as a boy. When Zahra grows up, she starts to feel the contrast between her lost identity, and the masculine character that she is obliged to acquire. Taylor, further, claimed that Ben Jelloun presents *Laylet el Qadr* as a myth that exposes hermaphrodite. Similarly, Brunel and Vion-Dury (2003) avered the point that Zahra succeeds in challenging the myth of hermaphrodite when she liberates her female identity from the veil that her father imposes on her. They also maintained that the use of myth in Moroccan literature has become an essential part because it represents the combination of two cultures. By the same token, Chapman, Ibnfassi, and Offord (2001) conceded the view that in *The Sand Child*, Zahra revolts against masculinity, and her androgynous state through suppressing her femininity, whereas in *Laylet el Qadr* she attempts to release her real gendered identity from her father’s constraints. Another important point, which Chapman et al., mentioned, is that Ben Jelloun employs metaphors that show abuse and male dominance through the absence of the mother and the sisters’ names in both novels. Chapman et al, further, proclaimed that the representation of bisexuality may lead the reader to build a false interpretation about Ben Jelloun’s message. They thought that he attacks Islam while his message is a criticism of pre-Islamic traditions when girls are buried alive to protect their fathers’ honor. Chapman et al. also reinforced their view arguing that Islam has put women in a good position, which has not been respected by most Muslim societies. Therefore, murdering females has been replaced by arranging their marriage, and directing their lives.

Heterosexuality and Rape

The current focus of Ben Jelloun’s fiction is to show how females are oppressed, and masculinity is given a prestigious position. Ouzgane (2011) has aptly expressed it when he argued that Ben Jelloun “dramatizes how virility emerges as the essence of Arab masculinity” (p. 74). Suzanne highlighted that this repression leads women to revolt against the rigid laws of society through committing prostitution. Eventually, sexual violence can be considered as a marker of North African societies, which favor virility as an aspect of honor. Consequently, females are obliged to follow males’ desires as in the case of Zahra when her father up brings her as a boy fearing his brothers’ humiliation because he has “produced only seven daughters” (Ouzgane, 2011, p. 74). She has searched for substitutions to take revenge from her father, and society as well through exploring heterosexuality.

To inspect closely and thoroughly, Ouzgane (2011) admitted the idea that heterosexuality has been linked with masculinity, virility, and “emerges as the act of penetrating other bodies” (p. 76). In other words, heterosexuality is seen as a source of man’s domination in most North African societies, whereas Ben Jelloun has made it way for self-liberation, and identity recognition through committing prostitution as in the case of Zahra. On the other hand, *Laylet el Qadr* has also explored rape as a form of

liberation after living 20 years as an androgynous person, Zahra starts to explore sexuality as a self-discovery through, firstly, throwing the Djalaba, and the bondage that her father obliges her to put, to hide her breast and, then through experiencing a rape with a strange man. Similarly, Hamil (2001) underscored that through heterosexuality, she witnesses the birth of her new identity. He concludes that through experiencing the forbidden, sexuality has become a sign of liberation from frustration and repression. Accordingly, Hamil (2001) demonstrated the idea that rape “offers Zahra an occasion to defy the code of chastity and to reclaim her female identity” (p. 74). In other terms, upbringing Zahra as a boy symbolizes the absent phallus, whereas rape represents the lost female identity.

Female Sexuality

It is an agreed fact that Islam deems female sexuality because women are treated with respect and represent the honor of their families. Sexuality is restricted by marriage; therefore any attempt to commit it represents repression or revolt against the norms. As far as the representation of female sexuality in Arabic literature is concerned, McFadden and Teixidor (2010) concurred that Muslim female characters, especially North African girls, mainly, Algerians and Moroccans, have attracted Western “imaginary and colonial fantasy, which then linked to some political agenda” (p. 49). They, further, inserted that after these countries have taken their liberation, the issue of women’s position in society has taken a new turn, and attracted some authors. In particular, those authors who have been influenced by Western spirit, and devoted their works to describe the female body. They also asserted that Ben Jelloun uses the female body in *Laylet el Qadr* as a tool for women’s emancipation from societal barriers. They confirmed that some critics consider that this novel participates “in presenting men as sex-craved and women as sex objects” (p. 49). In his part, Hamil (2001) believed that Zahra’s discourse on sexuality is an “ironic interrogation of the dogmatic discourse in (female) sexuality in the Arabo-Islamic world” (p. 74). Likewise, Ben Jelloun shows how Zahra discovers her female sexuality through repossessing “her body only in mythic time” (Hamil, 2001, p. 49). She becomes aware of the nature of her sexuality. Within this context, Hamil assessed Ben Jelloun’s use of female sexuality as a sign of femininity as opposed to masculinity and desire versus depression. Correspondingly, Gibbons (2010) speculated that *Laylet el Qadr* focuses, mainly, on female sexuality as its focal theme through which the author wants to show the reader how Zahra discovers her identity through “her sexual encounter with the Consul” (p. 117).

Sexual Transgression in Laylet el Qadr

According to Ben Jelloun (1991), literature tries to perform what is in society and shows some limits that cannot be touched such as taboos and sexual transgression. In his view, the literature of French expression paves the way for Arabic literature to explore the forbidden. This can be understood from his speech as follows:

En général, c’est dans le roman d’expression Française qu’on trouve le plus d’audace dans la contestation de l’ordre social et dans la transgression des tabous, surtout d’ordre sexuel [...] mais la principale originalité de cette littérature se trouve dans son rapport à la langue Française [...] Cette tentative

de dévoilement, cette porte ouverte sur un secret, sur un bien cache, est critiquée de manière sévère et souvent brutale par es intellectuels maghrébins arabophone. (As quoted in Hayes, 2000, p. 07)

Ben Jelloun, further, argued that Arab intellectuals, namely, Maghrebians have linked exposing taboos, and sexual transgression with the fact that Francophone writers are influenced by Western traditions. He also observed that novels like *L'Enfant de Sable*, *La Nuit Sacrée*, and *La Prière de L'absent* unveil the hidden secrets that most Arab societies consider taboo, and tend to challenge the social order by unveiling sexual transgression. For example, *Laylet el Qadr (The Sacred Night)* has exposed sexual transgression, and how females try to liberate themselves from the constraints of their societies by practicing prostitution.

An additional fact is that *Laylet el Qadr* is the transgression of sexual boundaries, and represents a reality that exists in Moroccan society, therefore it “undermines the ideology of realism” (Hamil, 2001, p. 72). Hamil believed that Zahra lives in a conflict between the conscious, and the unconscious sides. The first one imposes on her to be a male and the second one tries to push her to liberate herself and gains her female identity.

Given these points, it should be invoked that Ben Jelloun's *Laylet el Qadr* evokes many criticisms among Moroccan conservative intellectuals, especially after it has been translated into the Arabic language. This novel attempts to display a transgressed image of the eroticized body of females. Thereby, it challenges the borders of the Moroccan conservative society. In other words, the novel opens the gate for critics to look “beyond the veil of eroticism to bring out the authorial intention of eroticization”, this means that Ben Jelloun “publicizes the private, says the unsaid and unveils the veiled, by his representation of the erotic” (Ajah, 2013, p. 31).

Broadening these discussions considerably, all the images presented in the novel reflect an eroticized picture of the female body, and its sacredness in Muslim societies in general. This means that these images eroticize the readers not the characters through the use of taboo words. For this reason, the novel violates moral standards. Ajah (2013) wryly observed that Ben Jelloun does not question the relevance of Islamic norms, but how these morals are misinterpreted by Muslim societies. Following the same wave, Gerstner (2006) speculated that to transgress the religious, boundaries, and values, Ben Jelloun addresses sexuality, firstly, through sexual encounters of Zahra with other females in college and, subsequently with rape, and heterosexuality.

The Sacred in Laylet el Qadr

It is plausible to say that the appearance of the word sacred in the novel has raised much criticism among Muslim authors and critics. Notably, some critics have associated the beginning of the story with the death of her father on the 27th night of Ramadan, or what Muslims call *Laylet el Qadr*. Therefore, the death of her father signifies the end of her sufferance and the dawn of her freedom. According to Chapman, Ibnlfassi, and Offord (2001), Ben Jelloun mentions the term sacred in relation to Islam, and its sacred places among which is the mosque. Chapman et al, further, assumed that Ben Jelloun gives an indirect description of what is sacred in Islam to give an overview

of what is profane. In the light of what precedes, Chapman et al. (2001) wrote the following:

The eve of the twenty-seventh day of Ramadan is considered by Muslims to be the time when one's destiny is sealed. It is a sacred night for Muslims, hence the title of the novel. In the novel, the protagonist's destiny, indeed, going to take a different turn. (p. 53)

Chapman et al. also suggested that during this night, the protagonist's father liberates her, asks her for forgiveness, and names her Zahra, which means the beginning of a new life that "she was supposed to live as a woman" (p. 53).

Another sacred thing that Ben Jelloun mentions in the novel is *Laylet el Qadr*, which represents Muslim beliefs. Chapman et al. (2001) also affirmed that there are even sacred times, which are represented in the form of prayers that keep Muslims linked to religion, and far from profanity. They also contended that even Muslims have made their calendar sacred through the introduction of religious celebrations, and worship. In light of what has been discussed, Eliade (1965) said the following lines:

Le calendrier sacré se présente comme l' « éternel retour » d'un nombre limité de gestes divins, et ceci est vrai non seulement des religions primitives mais aussi de toutes les autres religions. Partout le calendrier des fêtes constitue un retour périodique des mêmes situations primordiales et, par conséquent, la réactualisation du même Temps sacré. (pp. 94-95)

What can be caught from what precedes is that Ben Jelloun has used *the holy night*, or *the sacred night* as a backdrop to show the reader the rebirth of Zahra, and her female identity, which is covered by her father in the form of a man. Furthermore, many French critics declare that Ben Jelloun attempts to show that even the female body is sacred in Islam. Equally important, Hamil (2001) also contended that Ben Jelloun has concentrated on the lives of ordinary people, mainly, females and how they suffer from societal restrictions. Ben Jelloun also insists on showing Zahra's imprisonment in her famous expression "قصتي هي سجنني" (my story is my prison) (Ben Jelloun, 1987, p. 135). According to Hamil (2001), Zahra suffers from different types of imprisonment as social, cultural, and political restrictions in addition to its representation in society.

Broadly viewed, employing the term sacred has raised controversy between religious critics because it represents an indirect criticism of what is sacred in Islam, and how it treats female sexuality, which has been restricted. Indeed, Ben Jelloun gives a misinterpretation of females' position that is valued positively in Islam.

Analysis

Through exposing female sexuality, which is the most tabooed subject in Islamic culture, Ben Jelloun introduces his readers into this forbidden field through which he transgresses the religious boundaries because he misinterprets Islamic standards. Notably, he resorts to taboo words related to female body parts, mainly, buttocks, thighs, and breasts. The main reason behind the overuse of expressions related to female body parts is to show the feminist side of Zahra. In other terms, he has given more

importance to the changes that affect the physical side of Zahra more than her psychological development. The following table lists the most tabooed subjects in the novel:

Table 1. *Taboo words in Laylet el Qadr*

Taboo words	Repeated Times	Page Number	Meaning in English
الغواية	1	37	The lure
الوركين او وركي	3	47-48	The hips
نهدايا او نهداها	5	34-47-60-68-98	My breasts or her breasts
قدالي	1	47	My nipples
الجنس	1	48	Sex
الفخذين	1	58	Thighs
الرغبة	1	69	The desire
ردفاها او ردفايا	5	48-97-98	Buttocks
الشهوة	6	36-98-101-106-125	The lust
يشتهي	3	42-106	He desires
قحبة	1	109	A prostitute
المتعة	5	36-69-99-125	The joy
الحب	3	84-97-98	Love
الحبيبة	1	51	Sexual partner
القبلات	1	51	Kisses
المداعبات	1	51	Tickles
منيه	1	94	His semen
حشرجاته او حشرجاتي	2	99	A sound after reaching orgasm

Sexual Discourse in Layet el Qadr

At the outset, it is made clear that *Laylet el Qadr* is a tale of sensuality that links the profane with the sacred, to violate Islamic standards. Ben Jelloun makes erotic language a medium to realize his hidden aims. This language serves as a touchstone to revolt against the “symbolic presence of the Name-of-the-Father-the figure of the law par excellence-in the unconscious that is responsible” (Hamil, 2001, p. 63). Ben Jelloun shows the symbolic revenge of Zahra through taking all her things and burying them with the dead body of her father, then she hangs him with the cover that he obliges her to put to hide her breast.

Coming back to the issue of female sexuality in *Laylet el Qadr*, Ben Jelloun makes Zahra's body and desire for sexuality an instrument for his sexual revolution against Islamic standards on one hand, and searches for fame between Western writers on another. Besides, Ben Jelloun appoints that Zahra regains her female identity through, firstly, prostitution, then her acceptance of her first male character, since it is the first, which builds the touching stone for her sexual identity. It is her relationship with the Consul, which helps her to forget.

As far as the use of sexual language in the novel is concerned, *Laylet el Qadr* is rich in sexual features, and sentences that reflect most tabooed topics such as sexual intercourse, prostitution, and the description of male/female body parts. Notably, Ben Jelloun focuses, mainly, on the transformation of Zahra's body from masculinity to femininity through developing her sexual desire, firstly, through rape, then adultery as it is explained in the following table:

Table 2. *Sexual discourse in Laylet el Qadr*

Sexual Discourse	Repeated Times	Page Number	Meaning in English
كانت تمسد اعضاءه	1	67	She attracts his organs.
قبولات مكتومة	1	67	Hidden kisses
لاح عضوه منتصبا	1	67	His erect penis appears
ردفاها منتفخان جدا	1	97	She has too fat buttocks
تدياها جميلا	1	98	Her breasts are beautiful
لحمية الشفتين	1	98	She has fleshy lips
تركته عضوه يلوح فيا	1	98	I let his organ inside me
فكانت الشهوة تعاود جسدي	1	98	The desire returns to my body.
كنت اكتشف المتعة لأول مره	1	99	I explore the joy for the first time
وتمرير شهتاي على رقبته	1	101	Passing my lips on his neck
كان يمضي لحظات طويلة في تفرس بيده مجموع جسدي	1	101	He spent moments touching my body
انت سوى ثقب بين ساقين نحيفين	1	125	You are just a hole between two thin legs

Discussion

The Analysis revealed that heterosexuality is the central objective that the author strives to explain. In Arab culture, heterosexuality is regulated by Islamic norms through legal marriage. However, Ben Jelloun undermines the heterosexual situation of women and exposes the different resulting tabooed phenomena that most Muslim countries suffer from including rape, adultery, and prostitution. The collected data also showed that the novel regards female sexuality as a refuge for women to prove their identities. Ben Jelloun exposes heterosexuality by giving much importance to show Zahra's body parts and how they receive her change from masculinity to femininity.

Although *Laylet el Qadr* shows Ben Jelloun's attitudes towards the use of taboo lexis, it is rich in euphemistic expressions. Besides, it is a problem to test the frequency of taboos in the novel since it is translated from French into Arabic, and words lose their power through their interpretation. Moreover, Ben Jelloun concentrates on describing sexual intercourse as a part of heterosexuality. He focuses on the heroine's socio-cultural conflict to prove her femininity. Zahra's lost female character is regained gradually through rape, adultery, and later on through prostitution as the following figure demonstrates:

Figure 1. Taboo Topics in *Laylet el Qadr*

The analysis demonstrated that Ben Jelloun introduced new linguistic features that express the use of taboo words. Besides, as the analysis also showed the frequency of taboo usage is high in the novel since both the writer undermined the socio-cultural background of the Arab societies in general and Moroccan society in particular. Ben Jelloun is regarded by many other Arab and Arab Francophone writers as a taboo breaker. Ben Jelloun mixes what is profane with what is sacred in Muslim culture.

Conclusion

Modern Arabic literature in general and Maghrebian Francophone literature, in particular, attract the attention of both Western and Arab critics. Minutely, postcolonial literature of North Africa, or what is called *littérature d'expression Française* has adopted Western theories with Classical Arabic models of myths, and narrative techniques. Among the emblematic figures of this literature is Ben Jelloun, who has become among the famous writers, sheds light on females' issues in general and sexuality as a form of emancipation in particular in almost all his novels, especially *The Sand Child*, and its sequel *The Sacred Night*. The latter offers the readers an overview of Zahra's journey towards liberty and regaining her female identity through committing prostitution. In other words, this journey enriches Zahra's experience as a woman because she, firstly, explores sexuality physically and, then emotionally through falling in love with the Consul.

Through the study of taboos in literary texts, may help in understanding the human psyche and the lexis used by some queer communities including homosexuals and lesbians. From this perspective, one might assume that *Leylat el Qadr* sought to approach the subject of sex and female sexuality, mainly in Arabi societies. It hunts to give subtle insight to criticize the cultural structure of Muslim societies. Consequently, it is not surprising to state that its publication and translation bring a wave of criticism

because Ben Jelloun has attacked the stereotypes of Muslim societies and how adultery is represented. Besides, Ben Jelloun deals with the different related topics to sexuality including the female naked body, orgasm and coitus which are surrounded by censorship in modern and post-modern literature and even in nowadays fiction. Consequently, the novel had been condemned and included in what is called *obscene literature*.

Last but not least, the overall purpose of the current research paper is to create a model to study the use of taboos in literature taking into account the socio-cultural background of the target society, stereotypes, social attitudes, and the different linguistic aspects, although this area of research has been dismissed from academic research because even investigating what is hidden may violate *the taboos* of the societies at hand.

Footnotes

1. It is a traditional cover used by most Maghreb females, to cover themselves from the head to the legs. However, it is replaced with what is called ‘djalaba’.

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